

The Insight and Purchase Reasons of Green Products Among Young Consumers - An Empirical Study

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ABSTRACT

Young consumers are none other than future market base. Their propulsion and trend determines the future of a product market. Green products and green marketing is becoming inseparable from consumers of present day. This paper sets focus on the younger consumers and their point of view of a green product, what are the factors that drive them towards a greener lifestyle. Primary data was obtained from 233 youngsters between 21 to 28 years of age, by a structured questionnaire survey. The statements focused on demographic characteristics along with environmental concern factors and elements involved in green product purchase. Our study reveals that religion, type of family and education played a major role in knowing about green products in a better way. Health, cost benefits and energy savings were much influencing the green product purchase. The overall knowledge about green products was more among young consumers irrespective of their gender.

1. Introduction

Green products are those which do not harm the environment or an individual at its production, consumption and disposition phases. Green marketing is nothing but the marketing of green products. Products that are environmentally friendly or products that emphasise on a sustainable environment are also called as a green product. Societal Marketing is the mainstream and green marketing is a sub division of it (Kotler, 1999). The environmental awareness among the European countries was more prevalent than the Asian sub continents during the early stages, but in recent times the cognizance has been carried to Asian continent also. It was first in the UNESCO conference held at Belgrade, which decided to create awareness among the people about safeguarding the environment and making them more concerned and involved (UNESCO 1977). Individual's attitude and belief reflects on their behaviour towards the wellness of their environment, it may be called as their environmental concern (Cohen, 1973; Hendee, 1972). "Green consumers", "Green Products" and "Green Marketing" were the terms used for people using eco-friendly products, products with eco-friendly labels and marketing of eco-friendly products (Peattie, 1997). The economic concept of how people satisfy their unlimited requirements with the limited resources available (McTaggart, Findlay and Parkin 1992, 24). Fulfilling infinite needs of humans with limited resources available (Polonsky, 1994). A consumer who avoids the product that is manufactured by causing damage to the environment, harming any animals, using more non-renewable energy resource, immoral examination upon animals or humans is called green consumer (Ellington, 1994). Manufacturing units throughout the world have increased their contribution towards green products by the demand and purchase interest created by the consumers (Sudir Sachdev, 2011). Reduction of material wastages, increased productivity and cost effectiveness drew the attention of manufacturing towards green manufacturing process (Azzone

and Manzini, 1994). By the end of nineteenth century the industrial perspective of green manufacturing magnified to academics which emphasised on consumer's perspectives such as attitude, purchase intention, behaviour and interest. (Bohlen et al, 1993). Advertisements played a major role in influencing the purchase of green products. Almost every firm started promoting its product as eco-friendly one with environmental safety as a connecting term (Keller 1987, Shearer 1990). The growth of green market was steady and in an increasing phase. It also made the marketing channels more structured and systematic (Fischer, K., & Schot, J, 1993). Some stated the growth to be positive and others stated the growth to be negative. But actually the growth of green market was at a positive upsurge (Schlegelmilch et al, 1996 and Menon and Menon, 1997). Though the interest shown by people was more, the actual numbers increased in purchase of green products was very minimal (Peattie, 1999). Globalisation was a major reason in proliferation of green market (Laroche, Bergeron, Tomiuk, & Barbaro-Forleo, 2002). The identification of right product for the right consumer and match their exact needs. Focus on new product development based on this strategy will help the organisation be more sustainable (Thogersen, 2002, D'Souza et al., 2006). Social organisations, consumers, stakeholders simultaneously demand in assurance in manufacture of eco-friendly products (Fischer et al., 2005). Many consumers considered it to be a lifestyle more than environmental concern. Premium pricing was not a problem as it was related to their social status. (Gil et al., 2000, Loureiro & Lotade, 2005). Consumers familiar with eco labelling and having prior knowledge were more interested in purchasing green products (Daugbjerg et al, 2014). In recent times, the attraction towards a product is based on its environment friendly elements rather than its commercial values (Gutierrez, A. M. J. A., & Seva, R. R. 2016). The thought of social concern and environmental friendly behaviour of an individual is incited to an individual through essential education (Meyer, 2015).

In this paper we focus on the sagacity of young consumers towards green products and the driving factors to their purchase. We have adopted primary data collection method to survey a sample population of 250 students from various educational institutions out of which 233 was found to be suitable after elimination of outliers and other errors. We do not confine them geographically as they represented different places. The paper tries to explain the actual opinion of youngsters about green product and why do they purchase them, with the help of collected data and statistical tools which are run with software support.

2. Objectives

1. To know factors responsible in determining the view of green products.
2. Green products view of with reference to various demographic factors.
3. To know factors responsible in determining the reasons of green products purchase.
4. Green products purchase reasons of with reference to various demographic factors.

3. Methodology

The methodology part originates with data collection. This study accentuates primary data by survey method. Sampling

Mean:

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
EnvirHarm	233	1	4	1.56	.627
ReusableMater	233	1	4	1.75	.719
Degradability	233	1	4	1.74	.728
MaxUtilofResources	233	1	4	2.31	.764
OrganicNatural	233	1	5	2.32	.847
NoNonRenew	233	1	5	2.43	.853
NoLivingOrganism	233	1	5	2.53	.904
PrefToExisting	233	1	5	2.36	.869
Fambenefits	233	1	5	1.73	.839
Energyeffi	233	1	4	1.69	.724
Health	233	1	5	1.73	.748
recomm	233	1	5	2.44	.839
Socialrecog	233	1	5	2.50	.861
Nochoice	233	1	5	2.73	.994
Impress	233	1	5	3.25	1.048
Insitfamily	233	1	5	3.23	1.036
Inspired	233	1	5	2.75	1.034
Valid N (listwise)	233				

The mean value of the statements representing the view of green product among consumers was measured. The five point likert scale statements ranging from 1 to 5 represents strongly agree to strongly disagree. The statements are sequenced based on their mean values ranging from lowest to highest. The

random sampling method was followed. A structured questionnaire consisting demographic variables like age, gender, occupation, marital status, family type and family income along with statements that supported consumer's view about green product was measured by using five point Likert scale (strongly agree to strongly disagree). A set of eight statements quantifying the consumer's aspect of green product was used. The computable values were analysed using SPSS to measure mean which measures the average response, factor analysis fragmenting the statements into two different groups with similar functions and ANOVA to study the significant difference between the groups.

- Sampling method: Simple random sampling, probability technique
- Questionnaire: Structured Questionnaire
- Software: Excel, IBM SPSS
- Statistical tools: Mean, factor analysis, ANOVA

4. Analysis

Data cleaning: The data collected from the survey was cleaned and processed by checking for missing values and outliers with the help of Microsoft excel. Normality and reliability tests were carried out. After completing the earlier stages, 233 data were obtained in total.

lowest values represent the higher level of responsiveness and the highest values represent the lowest responsiveness. Respondents were more concerned about the environmentally harmful products, the degradability of the products and the material which the product is made of. They were least

significant for both reason 1 and reason 2. Type of family was not significant for reason 1, but found to be significant for reason 2. Education level was found to be significant for both reason 1 and reason 2. The type of family and educational level

was found to be significant for reason 2, all the other combined factors was not significant. The significance values along with r square and adjusted r square values are listed below in table 5.

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender_1	Concern1	.088	.088	.038	.845
	Concern2	45.641	45.641	6.442	.012
Religion_1	Concern1	58.831	14.708	6.381	.000
	Concern2	75.704	18.926	2.671	.033
Typeoffamily_1	Concern1	34.402	11.467	4.975	.002
	Concern2	111.357	37.119	5.239	.002
Educationlevel_1	Concern1	5.816	2.908	1.262	.285
	Concern2	8.599	4.299	.607	.546
Gender_1 * Religion_1	Concern1	.212	.106	.046	.955
	Concern2	48.742	24.371	3.440	.034
Gender_1 * Typeoffamily_1	Concern1	.258	.258	.112	.738
	Concern2	.061	.061	.009	.926
Gender_1 * Educationlevel_1	Concern1	3.254	3.254	1.412	.236
	Concern2	14.290	14.290	2.017	.157
Religion_1 * Typeoffamily_1	Concern1	50.232	25.116	10.896	.000
	Concern2	128.814	64.407	9.091	.000
Religion_1 * Educationlevel_1	Concern1	1.843	.921	.400	.671
	Concern2	10.864	5.432	.767	.466
Typeoffamily_1 * Educationlevel_1	Concern1	16.884	8.442	3.662	.027
	Concern2	26.396	13.198	1.863	.158

Note: i. R Squared = .228 (Adjusted R Squared = .127), ii. R Squared = .235 (Adjusted R Squared = .135)

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender_1	Reasons1	.001	1	.001	.000	.989
	Reasons2	25.580	1	25.580	1.467	.227
Religion_1	Reasons1	37.042	4	9.260	3.549	.008
	Reasons2	198.459	4	49.615	2.846	.025
Typeoffamily_1	Reasons1	3.878	3	1.293	.495	.686
	Reasons2	174.404	3	58.135	3.335	.020
Educationlevel_1	Reasons1	58.673	2	29.336	11.242	.000
	Reasons2	48.488	2	24.244	1.391	.251
Gender_1 * Religion_1	Reasons1	.518	2	.259	.099	.906
	Reasons2	33.606	2	16.803	.964	.383
Gender_1 * Typeoffamily_1	Reasons1	.111	1	.111	.043	.837
	Reasons2	.137	1	.137	.008	.929
Gender_1 * Educationlevel_1	Reasons1	1.407	1	1.407	.539	.464

	Reasons2	20.833	1	20.833	1.195	.276
Religion_1 * Typeoffamily_1	Reasons1	1.700	2	.850	.326	.722
	Reasons2	7.448	2	3.724	.214	.808
Religion_1 * Educationlevel_1	Reasons1	1.315	2	.657	.252	.778
	Reasons2	3.039	2	1.519	.087	.917
Typeoffamily_1 * Educationlevel_1	Reasons1	1.872	2	.936	.359	.699
	Reasons2	131.386	2	65.693	3.768	.025
Note: i. R Squared = .217 (Adjusted R Squared = .113), ii. R Squared = .182 (Adjusted R Squared = .074)						

5. Results and discussion

The evaluation an individual's attitude, behaviour or another person's attitude, behaviour with regard to its impact on the environment is considered as environmental concern (Weigel, 1983; Ajzen, 1989). The study was about exploring the factors which really made a consumer feel that what were the characteristics of a product to be eco-friendly one. The factor analysis results of our study proved that degradability of a product and recycling capacity of a product were a major opinion for consumers to define a product as a green product. This indirectly means that the signs and symbols carried in the labels of a product influence the purchase of the product to an extent. Symbolic meanings in consumer goods have higher impact on use of product (Holbrook & Hirschman, 1982; Sirgy, 1985). A product must attract a consumer on its first sight, which is by its appeal and packing plays a major role in that (Rowan, 2000). Similarly, the main reason of purchase was mentioned

to be a products health benefits, family benefits such as cost and quality and energy efficiency. A 6% increase of price their food products for they are pesticide free is highly accepted and welcomed by young consumers (Cranfield and Magnusson, 2003). The growing awareness among the consumers in the recent days are also a part in selective purchase decisions. An individual's gender, educational level, type of family and religion were major influencing factors in knowing about a green product. The study also revealed that religion, type of family and educational level were major influencing factors for purchase in contrast to gender. The major limitation about the study was the number of samples, followed by geographic and cultural limitations. The scope for the study extends to vast dimensions such as increasing the number of demographic factors; including factors responsible for purchase intention may be economic or social, concentrating on a niche population and product specific study.

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